

Appendix A

Table A1. Oligonucleotide primer sequences used for ERV detection for Taqman[®] assays.

ERV	Oligonucleotide
WE8_F (syncytin-1)	TaqManAssayThermo
WE8_R (syncytin-1)	Hs01926764_ul
FRD (syncytin-2) F	TaqManAssayThermo
FRD (syncytin-2) R	Hs01942443_sl
HR_F	TaqManAssayThermo
HR_R	Hs04184598_sl
RDR F (receptor for syncytin1)	TaqManAssayThermo
RDR R (receptor for syncytin1)	Hs01056542_ml
MFSD-2 F (receptor parasyncytin2)	TaqManAssayThermo
MFSD-2 R (receptor parasyncytin2)	Hs00293017_m1

Table A2. List of analyzed ERVs.

ERV	Immune System Function	Reference
H-W (syncytin-1)	Immunoregulator	Blaise <i>et al.</i> (2005) [14]
H-FRD (syncytin-2)	Immunoregulator	Blaise <i>et al.</i> (2005) [14]
H-R (ERV3-1)	Immunoregulator	angenev <i>et al.</i> (2007) [59]

Table A3 List of transcription factors and cytokines analyzed during array assay.

	Gene	Oligonucleotide
	<i>FOXP3</i> forkhead box P3	PPH00029C
	<i>GATA3</i> GATA binding protein 3	PPH02143A
Transcription Factors	<i>RORC</i> RAR related orphan receptor C	PPH05877A
Array Catalog Number 330171	<i>STAT1</i> Signal transducer and activator of transcription 1	PPH00811C
CLAH25383	<i>STAT3</i> Signal transducer and activator of transcription 3	PPH00708F
	<i>IL10</i> interleukin 10	PPH00572C
	<i>IL17A</i> interleukin17a	PPH00537C
	<i>IL6</i> interleukin 6	PPH00560C
	<i>IL12A_p35</i> interleukin 12a	PPH00544B
	<i>IL23A_p19</i> interleukin 23 α	PPH01688B
Cytokines	<i>IL33</i> interleukin 33	PPH17375E
Array Catalog Number 330171	<i>IL1B</i> interleukin 1 beta	PPH00171C
CLAH25383	<i>TGFB1</i> growth factor 1 beta	PPH00508A
	<i>IL4</i> interleukin 4	PPH00565B
	<i>IL5</i> interleukin 5	PPH00692B
	<i>IFNA1</i> interferon alpha 1	PPH01321B
	<i>IFNB1</i> interferon beta 1	PPH00384F
	<i>IFNG</i> interferon gamma	PPH00380C

Table A4. Reference genes were used as controls for the experiment.

ERV	Oligonucleotide
<i>GAPDH</i> (Ref.)	TaqManAssayThermo
	Hs03929097_g1
<i>RNA18S1</i> (Ref.)	TaqManAssayThermo
	Hs99999901_s1

Table A5: Classification and function of interleukins and transcription factors. Numbers correspond to the references listed below.

Classification	Genes	Functions
Th1 cytokines	<i>IFNG</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Increase in recognition of antigens [1]. · Activation of Th1 immune response and inflammation [2]. · Antiviral defense: induction of NOS (nitric oxide synthase), that inhibits viral replication [3]; impediment of many stages of viral life cycle: entry, replication, gene expression, stability, release and reactivation [3].
	<i>IL1B</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Host defense against viruses [4,5]. · Induction of differentiation of Th17 cells [6].
Type I interferons	<i>IFNA1</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Rapid antiviral defense against early infection and inhibition of virus proliferation [7].
	<i>IFNB1</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Activation of STAT1 and expression triggering of interferon-stimulated genes, with a consequent decrease in viral replication [8].
Transcription factors	<i>STAT1</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Activation of interferons alpha and gamma [9]. · Antiviral defense [9,10].
	<i>STAT3</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Proviral factor in various infections: hepatitis C virus, varicella-zoster virus, HBV, HCV, HSV-1, human CMV and measles virus [11]. · Antiviral role in other infections: enterovirus 71, severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus and human metapneumovirus [11].
	<i>TBX21</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Stimulation of IFN-γ production and activation of antigen-specific T lymphocytes by dendritic cells. On the other hand, IFN-γ augments T-bet secretion as positive feedback [12]. · Reduction of Th2 (Liu [13] and Th17 responses [14,15]. · Development, maturation and stabilization of natural killer cells [16].
	<i>GATA3</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Development and proliferation of natural helper cells [17]. · Activation of Th2 and inhibition of Th1 response [18]. · Development of thymocytes [19]. · Activation of Foxp3 expression and activity regulation of regulatory T (Treg) lymphocytes, with maintenance of immune homeostasis and immunological self-tolerance [20].
	<i>FOXP3</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Autoregulation [21]. · Control of Treg cells generation, development, differentiation, function, maintenance, stability, phenotype and self-tolerance [21,22].
	<i>RORC</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Induction of Th17 differentiation [23]. · Inhibition of Th1 response [23]. · Contribution for differentiation of innate lymphoid cells [24].
	Pro- and anti-inflammatory cytokines	<i>IL12A</i>
<i>IL33</i>		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Pro-inflammatory: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> * Production of Th2 cytokines and inflammation associated with them [28]. * Reduction of viral replication [29]. · Anti-inflammatory: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> * Differentiation of alternatively activated macrophages, resulting in decreased inflammation and induction of tissue repair [30].
<i>TGFB1</i>		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Inflammatory: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> * Induction of Th17 lymphocyte differentiation [31]. · Anti-inflammatory: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> * Maintenance of T lymphocyte homeostasis [32] and tolerance [31]. * Inhibition of CD4+ T cell response in the periphery [33]. * Impediment of Th1 lymphocyte differentiation [31].
Th2 cytokines	<i>IL10</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Restriction of Th1 response [34] and IL-12 release [27]. · Deactivation of macrophages [35]. · Reduction of TNF-α and H₂O₂, that have antimicrobial action [35].
	<i>IL4</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Activation of resting B lymphocytes [36] and T cells [37]. · Increase in proliferation of mast cells [37]. · Decrease in the production of IFN-α [38].

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Figure A1. Summarized methodology.

